

Child Abuse And Its Negative Repercussions On His Future Life, From The Viewpoint Of The University Of Jordan Students

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Abstract

This study aimed at identifying child abuse and its negative repercussions on his future life from the viewpoint of the students of the University of Jordan. The aim of this study was achieved through developing a questionnaire consisting of (15) paragraphs that were divided into three axes: the social and psychological axis and the effects of abuse on the future of children. On a sample of (50) male and female students from the University of Jordan, the results of the study summarized that the most important effects of abuse on the social side came in the first place represented in the possibility of abused children deviating with an arithmetic average (4.16), followed by the abuse on the psychological side represented in the possibility of the child's tendency to Rapid reactions increase by an arithmetic average (4.15), as for the effects of abuse on the future of children, as these effects are represented by the difficulty of forming a future life for a child who is socially abused, by an arithmetic average (4.04), and finally with regard to the variable of academic specialization, it has The results showed that there were statistically significant differences in favor of social sciences students in the three fields of study.

Introduction

The phenomenon of child abuse and its negative reflections, And not to satisfy their psychological, social and personal needs, and neglect are among the most important problems that may directly affect the life and growth of the child and make him practice various forms of deviant and aggressive behaviors, low self-esteem, academic problems, and social withdrawal on others in the future. His social relationships with others and with his family in the community (James, 1994), the family represents the backbone of society to satisfy the child's psychological and social needs, including a sense of security and reassurance in the family and his self-confidence, and children are the product of the family that carries out its role in raising them, caring for them and refining their personality, especially in childhood, which is one of the most important stages of human development from all psychological, social, mental and other aspects As interest in the phenomenon of child abuse appeared in many Western and Arab societies and at the national level, however, there is still a need for many studies dealing with this phenomenon from the point of view of sociology, education, law and psychology, to study child abuse and its negative reflections on his future life.

1- **The study Problem:** the phenomenon of child abuse is of interest to many interested people in the human, social and statutory sciences, and often it may be negatively reflected in children's relations with the social environment in which they live, which affects the future of the family, and abuse here is not intended only as physical abuse, but there is psychological, social and emotional abuse and sexual harassment. Which may accompany them in their lives and which have negative effects on their growth and integration in society, whether in the short or long term. Therefore, the study problem can be summed up by knowing the effects and reflections of child abuse from the point of view of university students.

2- **The study important:** The phenomenon of child abuse in all its various forms generates psychological, social, health and emotional effects, personal development and the extent of social adaptability to the surrounding environment, and that children they are the men of tomorrow and the decision makers, and the importance of this study stems from the fact that the problems facing children affect and are reflected in their personal and social condition. And the extent of their adaptation in society. The study derives its importance from the expected results related to knowing the future repercussions of child abuse from the viewpoint of Jordanian university students. In terms of application, the results of this study will contribute to presenting a clear picture by knowing the most important future impacts and reflections on the life of a violent child through the planning process by setting up counseling, preventive and treatment programs to reduce the phenomenon of violence against the child, whether it is psychological, physical, social, emotional or sexual and how Dealing

with these cases and the results are of future importance for how to cooperate with these cases by proposing the best methods and strategies to reduce the problems that affect the development of children.

3- Study Questions: The current study attempts to answer the following questions:

The first question: What are the effects of the abuse and its future reflections on the social and psychological aspect of the child?

The second question: What are the effects of abuse and its reflections for the future of children?

The third question: Do the study sample individuals' estimates of child abuse differ according to the academic specialization?

4- Study Objectives:

The current study aims at the following:

1- Knowing the effects of child abuse and negative reflections on the social and psychological side.

2- Knowing the effects of child abuse and its negative reflections on children's future.

3- Knowing the extent of the different estimates of the study sample for child abuse according to the different academic specialization.

5- **Study limits:** The study is determined as follows:

1- **The time limit:** The study is limited to the abuse of the child and its negative reflections on his future life from the viewpoint of the students of the University of Jordan, the second semester of the academic year 2019/2020 month (January).

2- **Place and Objective Limit:** This research is limited to determining the impact of child abuse and its reflections on his future, from the point of view of the study sample.

3- **The human limit:** This research is limited to students of the University of Jordan.

4- The results of the study are determined by the nature of the tool and its validity and reliability connotations.

Procedural definitions:

Child abuse: It is the material and moral methods that individuals in society follow against children and it takes multiple physical and moral forms.

Violence against children: It is the use of force to express dissatisfaction with a specific issue or to achieve one of the goals, using different material and moral means.

Reflections: They are the effects that appear on the child, whether from a personal, social or psychological point of view, which affect his future.

6- Theoretical framework and previous studies

Violence: There is a difficulty in defining an accurate concept of violence, as terms and meanings are used such as aggression, and harm to others and their property. Violence is defined linguistically as a breach of the matter and lack of affection for it, and it is against compassion, and the most violent thing: that is, taking it too hard, and violence is censure and blame (Ibn Manzur, 1956).

(Redcross, 2002) defined violence as "a state that reflects the health and security of society and results from neglect of human economic, social, political, and institutional needs, and includes material and intangible harm that causes sabotage, pain, injury, and fear."

As a result of the growing manifestations of abuse and abuse of children at the global, Arab and local levels, the voices calling for confronting this phenomenon increased and led to the intensification of global, Arab and local efforts to demand the rights of the child and protect him from abuse in all its forms through a set of decisions and agreements adopted by the United Nations international, and the sessions were And the special studies conducted by the United Nations that aimed to urge the countries of the world to complete what had not been implemented of the goals of the World Declaration of the Rights of the Child (United Nations, 2006).and the studies carried out by the World Health Organization (2005) and the global initiatives (2006) and the previous initiatives and charters at the Arab level, which were exemplified by the efforts issued by the League of Arab States to protect children from abuse in the "Arab Child Charter in 1983" and the Arab Framework Document for the Child in 2001 The Arab Plan for Childhood Care and Development (1992). Jordan's ratification of the Convention on the Rights of the Child is based on national strategies and plans related to childhood, which include the National Early Childhood Strategy (2000), the National Early Childhood Plan (2003-2007), the National Strategy for the Elimination of the Worst Forms of Child Labor (2003) and the draft National Youth Strategy (2005-2009). And the strategic recommendations for the national study of underprivileged children and commitment to international covenants on childhood, such as the Convention on the Rights of the Child and the second Arab ten-year plan (2004-2015), according to which the Jordanian National Plan for Childhood (2004-2013) was launched, evidence of the importance of studying this phenomenon,severalgovernmental and non-governmental organizations began developing programs aimed at protecting children from abuse and providing them with safe centers through national awareness campaigns (the Jordanian National Plan for Childhood (2004-2013).”Jordan also responded to global calls through the National Council for Family Affairs in cooperation with a representative office Global Health in Jordan, by developing the Jordanian report on health and violence that includes assessing the problem of violence at the national level and developing appropriate strategies to combat violence and prevent its health and social effects, as an attempt to form a

scientific reference to be added to the balance of studies and research to know more about violence, its causes and effects in Jordan. These pioneering efforts led the World Health Organization to accredit the National Council for Family Affairs as an international cooperation center for protection from violence (Al-Samadi, 2007).

7.1- Domestic violence and its repercussions on children: The impact of domestic violence differs from one person to another and according to the type of violence practiced and the person who performs it in addition to the gender of the child if it is male or female, and the relationship of the victim to the aggressor and his relationship with those around him. Children who are exposed to violence are often ready to practice the same violence against themselves and others in addition to the occurrence of depression, suicide and criminality. The study conducted by Karlen (1996) indicated the following:

- The inability to deal positively with society and the optimal investment of self and environmental energies to obtain good production.
- Lack of feeling satisfied and gratified from life and private and public relationships.
- The inability of the individual to form normal attitudes towards himself.
- Inability to cope with stress and pressure in a positive manner.
- The inability to solve the problems facing him without hesitation or fear.
- The individual does not achieve independence in managing his life.

Some studies also indicate the existence of a relationship between children's exposure to family violence and the occurrence of behavioral disorders in them, especially aggressive behavior, as harsh upbringing that subjugates the child, punishes him physically, and hurts him psychologically develops his aggression and makes him fail to develop control of anger and aggression: (Al-Zahrani, 2005).

7.2- Facts and figures about the phenomenon of violence:

In 1998, Jordan witnessed about 270 cases of physical and sexual abuse, in 1999 about 522 cases, in 2000 AD 613, in 2001 AD 564 cases, in 2002 AD 661 cases, in 2003 AD 1178 cases, in 2004 AD 1423 AD, and in 2005 AD 1796 cases (Family Protection Department, 2006), In Jordan, the percentage is still not fully known at the general level, but the Specialist Hospital conducted a study of the cases that were reviewed by the hospital, and it was found that in 1994 AD, 33 cases were recorded between beating wives, suicide and abuse of children. In 1995, 45 cases were recorded, but in a recent study 2002, 300 cases were recorded in which women were subjected to abuse (Assal, 2003).

Although this phenomenon is widespread and known in all developing and non-developing societies However, the exact statistics of the extent of its spread in the Arab world in general and in Jordan in particular are inaccurate and completely unknown Because of the cover-up and the desire not to divulge, or the conviction that family problems are a private matter that cannot be discussed in front of others, or because of fear of a reaction and exposure to more violence.

7.3- Types of family violence:

First: Verbal violence: It refers to the verbal pattern that harms the child, and its destructive and common forms include harsh criticism, insult, contempt, reprimand, insult, rejection, belittlement and ridicule (Al-Masry, 2002).

Second: Home confinement and expulsion from the home: It is intended to prevent the individual from leaving or entering the house, and home confinement is widespread among some families for fear of the occurrence of the individual who is harmed (most of the females) in behavior that is considered an insult or offense to the family's reputation. If home confinement is practiced against females, then expulsion from the home is practiced against males, due to social considerations that distinguish Arab societies from others. This type of violence is the shot used by parents when they lose control over their children's behavior (Al-Tarawneh, 1999).

Third: Sexual violence: This form of violence is represented by the aggressor resorting to using his power and authority to engage in sex or carry out indecent sexual acts with the victim without the desire of the aggressor. Rape is the most dangerous form of sexual assault in the family and is often practiced under the threat of the aggressor to harm him if he does not yield to the desires of the perpetrator (Al-Qudah&Salloum, 2006).

Physical violence: Physical abuse or ill-treatment generally refers to physical harm inflicted on a child by one of his parents or relatives. It is not necessarily the result of a deliberate desire to harm the child. Rather, it is in most cases the result of harsh educational methods or strict physical punishment that have resulted in material harm to the child or almost. Physical abuse of a child often accompanies other forms of abuse. Physical abuse of a child includes bruises, fractures, scrapes, cuts, bites, and any other physical injury. It is considered assault as well as any violence practiced by a parent or family of a child if it causes bodily harm to the child. This includes striking with a tool or fist, slapping, burning, poisoning, suffocation, drowning, kicking and shaking. All these practices, even if they do not result in visible physical wounds or fractures, are considered an assault in and of themselves (Aljalbay, 2006).

7.4- The motives of family violence:The motives that lead the individual towards domestic violence can be divided into three sections, namely:

First: Self-motivation: These are the impulses that stem from the person and himself and which lead him towards domestic violence. This type of motivation can be divided into two parts:

One of the part self motivation: Which was formed in a person's soul as a result of external circumstances by neglect, abuse and violence that a person was subjected to since his childhood to other conditions that accompany the human being, which confirmed the accumulation of various psychological impulses, and resulted in a psychological complex that ultimately led to compensation for the aforementioned circumstances by resorting to Violence in the family. Violence is explained by the frustration theory that violence and aggression are always preceded by a state of frustration and that aggression is a function of the self that appears for the individual when feeling frustrated (Tawfiq 2003). Secondly part The motives that a person has borne since his formation, which arose as a result of behaviors contrary to Sharia that the parents had committed, which reflected the effect of their formation on the child. Genetic factor can be included among these drivers (Al-Dwibi, 2004). Recent studies have shown that a child who was subjected to violence during his childhood is more inclined to use violence than a child who was not subjected to violence during his childhood. Psychologically, violence also focuses on aggression as an innate instinct that expresses the individual's desire to die, as well as on the personality of the individual and the role of personal disorders, frustrations, psychological complexes, conflicts, emotions, anxiety and depression that the individual suffers from and their role in the occurrence of violence (Al-Shathely, 2001). But the biological explanation of violence, It focuses on the existence of a relationship between violence and the genetic makeup of the individual. From the point of view of the proponents of this theory, the front-side region and the peripheral system are responsible for the emergence of aggressive behavior in the individual, and the owners of this biological view of violence believe that there is a relationship between the male hormone and aggression and this explains the presence of increased aggression in males Compared to females, the results of biological research on aggressive hormones in individuals indicated that the problems that the individual faces, such as fear, stress, and frustration, have a strong effect on the secretions of hormones that affect behavior.

Second: Economic motives: "Many researchers in social sciences believe that the human condition in which children live in society, whether Arab or Western societies, is nothing but a consequence of their bad economic situation which is almost responsible for all their other conditions (social, political and psychological (Alghrib, 2008) .These motives are in common with other forms of violence with domestic violence, but the difference between them is in the goals that aim behind the economic-motivated violence in the family environment to obtain economic benefits from the use of violence against his family, but this is a definition of the charge of disappointment and poverty that Its effects are reflected violently by the father towards the family, but in other than domestic violence, the goal behind the use of violence is to obtain material benefit. Many studies have confirmed that many behavioral methods such as cruelty in the treatment of children, psychological, sexual and physical abuse, and delinquency are found in a relationship. A clear correlation with the low economic factor of the family (Al-Abd Al-Ghafour and Ibrahim, 1998).

Third: Social motives: This type of motivation is represented in the customs and traditions accustomed to society and which require a man - according to the requirements of these traditions - a measure of manhood so that he does not beg to lead his family without violence and force. That is, they are the criterion by which it is possible to know the extent of manhood that a person is characterized by, otherwise he is lost among men. This type is directly proportional to the culture that society holds on the level of family culture, so the more the society is on a high degree of culture and awareness, and the more the role of this diminishes. Motivations are even absent in high-end societies, and on the contrary, in low-culture societies, as the degree of influence of these motives varies according to the degree of degradation of societies' cultures (Al-Mutairi, 2006).

Violence is also explained from the social approach that violence is an educated behavior through the process of social interaction with others, and this trend focuses on social values and the extent of the prevalence of the culture of violence in one community over another, as well as the circumstances surrounding the individual such as the family, the residential area, the school, and the local community, The Media, and the Group of Friends, (Al-Mutawa, 2004).

8. Previous studies:

Abdul-Jawad's study (2020) This study aimed to find out the relationship between domestic violence directed towards children and their practice of school violence within the framework of individual behavioral service. The results indicate the existence of a positive statistically significant relationship between the two variables and the possibility of predicting school violence through domestic violence directed at children within their families.

Raed study (2019) The study aimed to identify societal violence against children who are subjected to violence from the point of view of the mother and the center's teachers. The study sample consisted of (45) children in the Al-Amal Center for the Care of Violated Persons in Baghdad. the study found a high percentage of children who were subjected to domestic violence and there were no significant differences in the forms of societal violence from the viewpoint of the mother and the teacher.

Khalifa study (2018) This study aimed to identify the Appearances of domestic violence against children and their impact on society and strategies to reduce this phenomenon. This study concluded that socialization is the

most important factor that leads to the phenomenon of violence against children, and verbal and moral violence is one of the most common forms of violence that is exposed. It has children on a daily basis inside and outside the family, and domestic violence against children hinders comprehensive social development, stability and community security.

AL-Kassab study (2015) This study aimed to know the reality of domestic violence against children in Jordanian society from the point of view of the children themselves, as a questionnaire was prepared for this study and the results showed that the field of social violence came first, then physical and then psychological violence, and there are differences attributed to the gender variable In favor of females, and differences attributed to the father's education variable, and no differences attributed to the mother's education variable.

The study (Lynette & Shamra 2013) aimed to find out the characteristics of parenting and its great impact on the vulnerability of children to family violence. And to explore the role of women in the relationship between exposure to physical and psychological violence from an intimate partner and the understanding of children's external behavior problems. The data for this study were taken from three waves of families in alinoye state. the final sample included 1,653 children from 805 families. The analyses were conducted over two phases to better understand the unique relationships underpinning child development. As for children whose ages range from 6 to 12 years old, the results indicated that no direct or indirect pathways were found between exposure to domestic violence and behavioral problems, but there were behavioral problems for children between the ages of 13-17.

Al-Suwaiti study (2012) This study aimed to identify domestic violence directed at children, which includes physical and psychological violence and neglect, and its relationship to a sense of security in a sample of ninth-grade students in the city of alkhailil. The study sample consisted of (99) male and female students, and the researcher used the parental abuse scale and the scale (Maslow) Feeling of security The results showed that psychological violence ranked first, then neglect came second. There are no statistically significant differences in the mother's education level, as there are statistically significant differences in the father's education level on forms of violence.

In the United Nations Study on Violence against Children (2010), the results of the study showed that violence against children is practiced everywhere, regardless of their country, society, or social class. Excessive violence against children may make headlines, but children say that frequent small daily acts of violence and abuse hurt them as well. While some acts of violence remain unpredictable and isolated, violence against children is often perpetrated by individuals they know and trust, such as parents, friends or girlfriends, spouses and partners, classmates, or teachers and employers. Among the forms of violence against children is physical and psychological violence, such as insults, discrimination, neglect and abuse. Although the repercussions may vary according to the nature and severity of violence, the consequences for children and society as a whole are most of the time severe and harmful.

8.1- What distinguishes the current study from previous studies:

The previous studies focused on studying the following aspects: family violence against children and their practice of school violence (Abdul-Jawad, 2020, Al-Sweiti, 2012), the manifestations of family violence against children and its impact on society (Khalifa, 2018, Al-Kassab, 2015) and knowing the characteristics of parenthood and the role of socialization And its effect on children from domestic violence (Lynette & Shamra 2013). As for the current study, it was distinguished from previous studies through the study problem, which determines the effects of child abuse and its negative repercussions on his future life on the social and psychological level of the child.

9. Method and procedures (Study methodology):

9.1 Study method: The researcher used the descriptive and analytical method in this study.

9.2 Study population: The study population consists of students of the University of Jordan from the College of Arts and Educational Sciences, who are enrolled in the first semester of 2019/2020 in January.

9.3 Study sample: The study sample consists of (50) male and female students from the University of Jordan, who were chosen randomly.

9.4 Study tool: The tool consisted of two parts: the first included general information related to students, namely: specialization, study program, and marital status. As for the second section, it included the study scale, which consisted of (15) paragraphs that define the student through her response to them the implications and their importance by choosing one of the five-point answers chosen in Likert style, as follows: Strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, and strongly disagree) The following scores were given (5, 4, 3, 2, 1) respectively.

9.5 Validity of the tool: The validity of the tool was verified by presenting it to a number of arbitrators specialized in sociology, psychology and Sharia, and based on their opinions, the necessary modification was made.

9.6 Tool stability: The researcher applied the questionnaire to an exploratory sample from outside the study sample and consisted of 30 university students in two consecutive times separated between them, and used the Cronbach - alpha equation to measure between the fields of the tool, as well as to extract the value of stability calculated on the basis of the total score for all paragraphs, which is 0.78.

9.7 Study procedures: After determining the study sample, the questionnaire was distributed, after explaining its objectives and asking the sample to fill it accurately and objectively. The researchers also assured the sample members that the study is for the purposes of scientific research only and that all answers will be dealt with quite quickly.

9.8 Statistical processing: In order to process the data, use the Statistical Packages for Social Sciences (SPSS) program, using the following methods and procedures:

- 1- To answer the first, second and third questions, the arithmetic means and standard deviations were extracted.
- 2- To extract the stability of the tool, the stability factor (Corn Bach Alpha) was used.
- 3- The frequencies and percentages were extracted for sample counting purposes.

10- Presentation and discussion of results:

Table (1)
The frequencies and percentages of the demographic variables of the respondents

Variable	Categories	Iteration	Percentage
Specialization	Social Sciences	25	50%
	Educational sciences	25	50%
Course	Master	20	40%
	Bachelor	30	60%
Social status	Single	9	18%
	Married	22	44%
	Divorce	19	38%

Description of demographic variables: Table No. (1) shows a description of the demographic variables of the sample members, as they were as follows: Academic specialization: What percentage is 50% of students in social sciences, and 50% of students of specialization in educational sciences. Study program: 60% of the sample is undergraduate students, and 40% of master's students. Marital status: the vast majority of the study sample is 44% who are married, followed by 38% of the divorced, and only 18% of the single.

Results:

To answer the first question: What are the effects of abuse and future reflections on the social and psychological aspect of the child? The arithmetic means, standard deviations, and the level of significance were extracted, and they were as follows:

Table (2)
Arithmetic means, standard deviations, level of significance, observed, rank, and degree of rating of paragraphs for the effects of abuse on the child's social aspect

No	Paragraph	Average arithmetic	Standard deviation	The level of viewer significance	Rank	Grade
6	The risk of a violent child's delinquency increases.	4.16	1.04	.. ′.	1	High
2	A violent child tends to be afraid to deal with others.	4.12	0.95	.. ′.	2	High
(1)	A violent child tends to be isolated and lonely.	3.96	0.85	.. ′.	3	High
5	The child's violent behavior is characterized by indifference and nervousness	3.78	1.06	.. ′.	4	High
4	A violent child loses the ability to deal with society positively	3.64	0.97	.. ′.	5	High

3	The aggressive way a violent child treats others is aggressive	3.55	0.97	.. ‘.	6	High
College degree		3.87	0.66			High

The table shows that Paragraph No. (6), which states “the probability of delinquency for a violent child increases,” came in the first place and had the highest arithmetic average of (4.16), while Paragraph No. (2), which states: “A battered child tends toward fear of dealing with Others "are in the second rank, with an arithmetic average of (4.12), and the first paragraph, which states:" A violent child tends towards isolation and loneliness, is ranked third, with a mean of (3.96), and the fifth paragraph, which states: "The behavior of a violent child is characterized by indifference and nervousness is ranked fourth With a mean of (3.78), And came in the penultimate rank Paragraph No. (4), which states that “a battered child loses the ability to deal with society in a positive way,” with an average arithmetic of (3.64). Paragraph No. (3) came in the last rank, which states that “the way a violent child deals with others is aggressive,” with an average arithmetic mean of (3.55). As for the future effects of abuse on the psychological side of the child, they were as follows and as shown in Table (3):

Table (3)

Arithmetic means, standard deviations, level of significance, observed, rank and degree of appreciation for the paragraphs that make up the effects of abuse on the psychological side of the child

Number	Paragraph	Average arithmetic	Standard deviation	The level of viewer significance	Rank	Grade
10	A violent child tends to react quickly.	4.15	1.1	.. ‘.	1	High
11	A violent child is born with a sense of inferiority as a result of feelings of helplessness and fear.	4.02	1.08	.. ‘.	2	High
9	A violent child has more depressed feelings.	3.99	0.83	.. ‘.	3	High
8	A violent child has a low level of self-confidence.	3.67	1.08	.. ‘.	4	High
7	A violent child is more likely to develop mental illness.	3.45	0.68	.. ‘.	5	High
College degree		3.86	0.71	.. ‘.		High

Table (3) shows that Paragraph No. (10), which states “The battered child tends to react quickly,” came in first place with an arithmetic average of (4.15), while Paragraph No. (11) came which states: Inferiority as a result of feelings of helplessness and fear "in second place with an arithmetic average of (4.02). As for Paragraph No. (9), which states that" feelings of depression increase in the battered child, "it came in third place, and came second to last, Paragraph No. 8 which It states, "The battered child has a low level of self-confidence." With a mean arithmetic of (3.67), and paragraph No. (7) came in last place, which states: "The likelihood of a violent child suffering from mental illnesses increases." Arithmetic average (3.45).

To answer the second question, which states: What are the effects of abuse and the reflections it has on children's futures? Arithmetic averages, standard deviations, and the level of significance observed were extracted to know the future effects of violence on the child, and they were as follows and as shown in Table (4):

Table (4)

Arithmetic average, standard deviations, level of significance observed, rank and grade of the paragraphs forming the effects of abuse on the child's future

Number	Paragraph	Average arithmetic	Standard deviation	And the level of significance of the viewer	Rank	Grade
12	It will be difficult for a violent child to form a future life socially.	4.04	0.99	.. ‘.	1	High
15	Delinquency and engagement with bad friends as a result of negligence and lack of control	3.85	1.1	.. ‘.	2	High

13	A violent child is more likely to engage in violence against his or her children and his wife in the future.	3.75	0.86	.. ‘.	3	High
14	There is a high probability of failure both scientifically and practically.	3.55	1.25	.. ‘.	4	High
College degree		3.80	0.69	.. ‘.	5	High

Table (4) shows that Paragraph No. (12), which states “It will be difficult for a battered child to form a future life from a social point of view,” came first with a mathematical average of (4.04), while Paragraph No. (15) came which states: Deviation and engagement with bad friends as a result of negligence and lack of control, "in the second rank, with an arithmetic average of (3.85), and ranked third paragraph "The probability that a violent child will practice violence on his children and wife increases in the future," with an average of (3.75), and Paragraph No. (14) came in last place, which states: “There is a high probability of failure in terms of science and practice,” with an average of (3.55).

To answer the third question, which states: “Do the study sample individuals’ estimates of child abuse differ according to the different academic program (social sciences, educational sciences)? The arithmetic means and standard deviations, and (T) test for the answers of the study sample individuals

Table (6)

(T) test for two independent samples according to the variable of academic specialization

Domain	Specialization School	Average arithmetic	Standard deviation	Value t	Level of significance
raised the abuse on the social side	Educational sciences	3.8101	.80066	.004	.000
	Social Sciences	4.1129	.49241		
Provoked abuse on the psychological side	Educational sciences	3.9298	.82756	.005	.000
	Social Sciences	4.2640	.54254		
The effects of abuse on the child's future	Educational sciences	3.9034	.81233	.022	.000
	Social Sciences	4.1699	.60935		

The results shown in Table (6) indicate that there are statistically significant differences in the response of study individuals to its three domains: The differences in the three domains were in favor of students of the social sciences program, as the arithmetic averages were higher than the arithmetic averages of students of the educational sciences program in the three fields.

11- Discussing the results:

The results of this study showed that the most important future effects and repercussions of child abuse as seen by students and distributed in its three areas, the first is the social effects, and the first of which was the effects related to the probability of the delinquency of the battered child, with an average ratio of (4.16), then the child's tendency to fear dealing with others. This was followed by the child's tendency to isolation and loneliness, then the behavior of the violent child being indifferent and nervous, and finally the child's loss of the ability to deal with society in a positive way, and this contradicts the values, customs and behavioral patterns accepted in the society to which he belongs.

As for the child's family abuse and the extent of its contribution to the delinquent behavior of the child, this is confirmed by social and psychological theories, the feeling of fear, nervousness, and the loss of the ability to adapt to the circumstances surrounding the individual may lead to deviant behavior. It also stresses the importance of the family in the socialization of the individual, and that family problems and the accompanying abuse negatively affect the individual's acquisition of good values, customs and traditions, where the family lacks them, and the feeling that the home and family are ineligible to live, which affects the child's attitudes towards others.

The second field: Concerning the psychological aspect, the results of the study showed that the paragraph that states "A violent child tends to rapid reactions" came in first place, with an arithmetic average (4.15), the scale of the psychological effects of child abuse. This may be due to the psychological instability of the child and the lack of psychological adjustment due to the pressures surrounding the child, especially psychological and family pressures. The results also showed that the battered child has an increased sense of inferiority due to feelings of

helplessness and fear resulting from the abuse, which creates a feeling of social worthlessness, especially when he sees his peers from children who belong to socially and psychologically coherent families.

The results of the current study related to the third field, which is: the effects of abuse on the future of children, as these effects were represented by the difficulty of forming a future life for a violent child from a social point of view, with an average percentage (4.04), and the child's resorting to deviation with bad companions due to negligence and lack of control, and that the child The victim has a chance to practice violence against his family members, such as his wife and children in the future, and the child's chance of success in the scientific and practical aspects is low. The researchers believe that the abused and abused child suffers from many social and psychological problems that are reflected in his ability to adapt psychologically and socially, due to his loss of the basics of social upbringing, such as emotional and emotional stability in a family atmosphere full of love, good feelings, direction and attention.

As for the results related to the study sample's estimates of child abuse and related to the variable of academic specialization, they showed statistically significant differences in favor of social science students in the three fields of study. Researchers believe that this is due to the proximity of students of social sciences and their knowledge of social problems, especially problems of child abuse and domestic violence, as well as scientific knowledge of these problems.

11.1 Recommendations:

Based on the results of the current study and discussion of these results, the researcher recommends the following:

- 1- The importance of adopting the results of this study and working to circulate them to institutions working in the field of childhood.
- 2- Spreading public awareness aimed at building stable and ethical human relationships that care for and protect children and preserve their freedom from exploitation and abuse.
- 3- Work to expand the framework of the contribution and responsibilities of educational and administrative organizations, including school administrations, to be consultative centers to monitor this phenomenon, and to train cadres to help children talk about the types of abuse that they may be exposed to.
- 4- Conducting more studies on child abuse in Jordanian society in rural and urban areas.

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